

Border as Informal Public Space: Tracing Istanbul City Walls' Micro-Narratives

Ayşe Eda Adıgüzel

Research Assistant, Department of Architecture, Bahçeşehir University
PhD Student, Architectural Design Program, Istanbul Technical University
ayseeda.adiguzel@bau.edu.tr

Ahmet Bender Uğurlu

Research Assistant, Department of Architecture, Istanbul Technical University
PhD Student, Architectural Design Program, Istanbul Technical University
ugurli@itu.edu.tr

Serim Aygen Kıştın İşcan

Research Assistant, Department of Architecture, Antalya Bilim University
PhD Student, Architectural Design Program, Istanbul Technical University
aygen.kistin@antalya.edu.tr

ABSTRACT: Border is a dynamic existence that allows semantic changes, ruptures, and connections. While discussions on publicity in Istanbul can be addressed in different contexts, the layers of Istanbul can be unraveled in the pursuit of informal spaces by broadening the definition of "border." This article examines the Istanbul City Walls as dynamic borders that transform into informal public spaces through the narratives of localized micro-interventions. The potentials of the tectonic structure of the Istanbul City Walls define micro-scale occupation and intervention areas for inhabitants, transforming city borders into a palimpsest phenomenon. Mapping and collages are used as a method to categorize micro-narratives according to activities, contributions to publicity and tools for each micro-intervention that provides informal publicity. The study aims to bring together the informal narrative of Istanbul through the border with an alternative representation as a mapping of collages, enabling the prediction of future micro-narratives and informal publicities.

Keywords: border, informal public space, mapping, micro-narratives, intervention.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is my view that informality permeates every aspect of the functioning of society. It is a vast realm - a multiplicity of niches- where human beings place themselves, either prior to the advent of an imposed formal system or within the nooks and crannies of the formal societal system. They do so in order to deal effectively with the routine issues of everyday life. Informality is understood here as a reality not totally separated from the formal system but rather linked to and shaped by it. Informality is a structure of action that contains both harmonious (adaptation) and contradictory (resistance) relationships. It is a site of power in relation to external disciplinary and control power [1].

In this article, an alternative reading of informal public space which is also defined as Laguerre's definition [1] of a site of power is made by revealing the micro-narratives established by the tools, textures, activities, users and the micro-interventions that arise from them. Although the

informal is recognized in different fields, spatially and in an urban case, it is intertwined with the formal. According to Hernandez and Kellett [2], informality is not only defined within the dichotomy of formality, but also provides a motivation that includes cultural, social, and economic information. The way informality is handled in this article can be considered as revealing these layers. Being informal, which is considered as an important parameter of urban development, appears as a practice in which the city is produced [3]. Hernandez-Garcia [4] discusses this practice of production through a two-stage pattern. While the first one emphasizes the continuity and transience of change, the other presents a fiction of alternative space production through the activity of local people.

Although the production of informal space can be traced through different spatialities, Aldo Van Eyck's The City as Playground project, in which temporality and participation come to the fore [5], is considered as the project that guides the article. Accordingly, the fact that urban voids have become an alternative representation space for informal uses has directed the scope of the article to question the important components of the city such as public occupancy. At this point, the concept of "border" has become the backbone of the article due to notions such as urban space, continuity, permeability, change and accessibility. In this context, the article aims to construct an alternative narrative on how informal public spaces are created by focusing on the physical equivalent of the border, the Istanbul City Walls, which is one of the most important borders of Istanbul and the potential practices of space production it contains.

II. BORDER AS INFORMAL PUBLIC SPACE

Informality in urban areas can be understood as a dynamic and intricate process that challenges the traditional, static concept of the city as a fixed and permanent built environment. Informal spaces emerge

and evolve over time, often occupying different areas and adapting to the shifting needs of urban inhabitants. These spaces don't follow a standard classification system of the urban areas; they are characterized by fluidity, mobility, instability and temporariness [6]. Informality coexists with formal urban systems, creating a hybrid and ambiguous spatial relationship. According to Landry [7], the discussions about formality and informality should focus on alternative perspectives, emphasizing hybridity, simultaneity, and coexistence, recognizing both formal and informal orders as equally valid and simultaneous approaches to shaping the city.

Borders, as physical or conceptual spatialities, serve not just as elements of separation but as zones of interaction and potential transformation. Borders are traditionally understood as rigid and controlled spaces, creating territories and enforcing distinctions between nations, regions or spaces. However, in practice, borders often evolve into informal public spaces, shaped by the activities, interactions, and networks of the people who live near or cross them. Schoonderbeek [8] examines borders as intricate spatial phenomena that go beyond physical lines, barriers or boundaries. He challenges the conventional understanding of borders as static divisions; instead proposing that they are dynamic spaces of simultaneity where multiple political, social, and cultural processes intersect. He emphasizes the need for innovative mapping techniques to understand the complex nature of borders.

Dovey and King [9] examine the structure and visibility of informal settlements and spaces that operate autonomously outside governmental control. Although these spaces are often perceived as problematic and subjected to removal, such settlements are important dynamic components of urban life. They argue that informal settlements require more inclusive urban policies and a deeper understanding of their spatial structures and connections to the formal city. In this context, when informal public space and the concept of border are considered together, policies and locality establish a significant dichotomy.

The questioning of the tracking of informal occupations together with the concept of borders will be elaborated in the next section through the Istanbul City Walls challenging conventional understandings of borders by introducing informality as a central concept. These occupations provide alternative approaches to space production, emphasizing inclusion, creativity, temporality and shared agency. The narratives emerging from these occupations and interventions show how human-space relationships can be reimagined. They emphasize the importance of understanding and meeting people's spatial needs and desires. Rethinking the border of the city with principles of informality, supports creating place-based urban policies that achieve greater social and cultural inclusivity.

III. ISTANBUL CITY WALLS

The new meanings that the border attributes to the spaces it separates, the informally formed public spaces with its structure open to interventions and the relationships they establish with the physical parameters they transform are interpreted through the Istanbul City Walls, which is the most prominent border for the city (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - 3D Model of the Istanbul City Walls.

After the Ottoman Conquest in 1453, Istanbul City Walls lost their defense purpose, and became a part of civilian life accommodating diverse practices and communities. In the post-1980 period, the walled zone began to function as an urban fissure, positioned between two densely populated areas and marked by its complex, layered spatiality. Despite redevelopment efforts introducing green parks and reconstructed walls, the zone continues to host informal uses, embodying a heterogeneous and temporally layered urban environment [10]. Istanbul City Walls highlight the tensions between demolition and conservation during the period of rapid urban transformation. Especially the mixed legacy of the 19th century laid the foundation for modern conservation practices and the ongoing debates surrounding the preservation of historical urban landscapes [11]. Istanbul City Walls symbolize both the evolution of urban functions and the adaptability of historical structures. Evolving from a defense system to a flexible occupation zone with various social and spatial practices, the walls now accommodate informal uses, reflecting their dynamic role (Figure 2) in redefining the concept of 'border'. As a part of continuous transformation, Istanbul's city walls have the potential to create the dynamics of the system in which they are involved, as part of a reality that is constantly transforming, deteriorating, dissolving, re-forming, but never considered finished [12].

Figure 2 - Collage of the dynamism of Istanbul City Walls.

Today, when viewed from a macro scale, these borders create serious distinctions between urban settlement areas. However, when looking at micro-physical conditions and semantic relations, it is observed that they have moved away from the concept of border and the place it represents in the urban fabric, turning into new dynamic and public areas. One of the main objectives of the study is to investigate the spatial equivalents of micro-interventions nourished by the tectonic relations established by the city wall due to the settlement of different urban textures around it. The physical boundaries of the city walls are no longer as defined as before due to changing use and time; it has become a public input of the existing urban texture and has established an inseparable narrative relationship with other architectural elements and their users.

Özaydın [13] states that the City Walls are an interface to be perceived on two different levels. The first one is the City Walls as a concrete object that is perceived and looked at for the moment experienced; the other is the City Walls that can be perceived as a process determined by different layers in the dimension of time and can be perceived in the context of urban relations [13]. In the definition of the city wall, where perceptions and conceptions play a decisive role and different layers come together; the phenomenon that makes the wall exist as an interface is the tectonic spatialities it contains. The tectonic spatialities on the Istanbul City Walls can be addressed as niches, bastions, levelings, surfaces, arches and destructions (Figure 3). The fact that the tectonic spatialities form the character of the city wall makes it inevitable for micro interventions to bond with the environment. The city wall, which is defined as an interface, transforms itself into a palimpsest of phenomena that contains informal micro-narratives rather than an urban boundary.

Figure 3 - Tectonic spatialities of Istanbul City Walls.

IV. MAPPING THE MICRO-NARRATIVES

Frampton states that tectonics is a mode of assembling, reconstructing and interpreting and that tectonics is not only the product of a constructive framework [14]. In parallel, he expands the concept of tectonics with the concept of atectonics and explains that as a kind of concealment and unrevealedness. Within the framework of the daily life sections taken from the Istanbul City Walls, it is revealed that atectonics emerges in parallel

with the conceptual expansion drawn by Frampton and that the vital layers come into existence in the context of various micro scales through tectonic fiction. In the context of these micro-scale interventions and narratives, the collages of sections taken from the Istanbul City Walls are designed to provide a multifaceted alternative reading as the research method of the article. Thus, informal spatialities and their components along the city walls are revealed and mapped (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Mapping of Istanbul City Walls and section collages.

Within the framework of the analyses made on the city wall, it has been determined that the activity of reconstruction and interpretation inherent in tectonics defines a multidirectional relationship with human elements such as the urban texture, green texture and transportation line located around the city wall, and that the reflections of this relationship change with different temporal situations during the day and contribute to the formation of new informalities.

The nature of the micro-interventions on the observed tectonic situations is analyzed with the texture around the city wall, the tools and joint details that provide the intervention. While the transformative layers such as diversity of the user, usage timeline and the profile of the intervention dynamize the wall's surroundings, the functioning and method of use resulting from the type of intervention also dynamize the wall as a whole. For instance; the niche tectonics of the city wall fragment has gained new functional meanings such as warehouse of a cafe (Figure 5) and car parking area (Figure 6) nourished by the surrounding context and user profile; micro interventions spread over temporal layers have been achieved through the unification of micro interventions through the requirements of these layers. Here, the informality established by the niche has been followed as areas that allow occupation, since it creates a defined area and can be used as a closed volume.

Figure 5 - Section collage of a niche occupied as a warehouse by locals.

Figure 6 - Section collage of a niche occupied as car parking area.

These micro-interventions collectively highlight the informal uses of the Istanbul City Walls, illustrating how such activities transform the city's most prominent border into an active participant in urban life. Bastions are enclosed with wooden elements such as doors or panels, repurposing them as workshops (Figure 7); ropes tied between nails driven into the walls create informal laundry-hanging spaces, responding to the immediate needs of users (Figure 8). These adaptive uses show how the city walls are constantly reinterpreted by their context and users, adding new layers of meaning and functionality. Rather than functioning solely as a boundary, the walls become spaces of interaction between city and its inhabitants.

Figure 7 - Section collage of a bastion used as workshop area.

Figure 8 - Section collage of a bastion with micro-intervention with rope.

The arches, which are another essential component of the city walls, have also shaped the informal fiction of the publicity today with their feature of being a passage. The arches of the city walls serve as passageways for vehicles and pedestrians, redefining their function within the urban landscape (Figure 9&10). Unlike other micro-narratives, the interventions within this tectonicity are characterised as formal interventions in an urban context, but are considered as an informal publicness in terms of the change in usage practices over time.

Figure 9 - Section collage of an arch used as a vehicle line.

Figure 10 - Section collage of an arch used as a pedestrian line.

The orchards identified with the City Walls and the levelling of it are analysed as textures that had a direct impact on the formation of public spaces. The inhabitants

of the nearby areas have turned these zones into narratives where they utilised plant cultivation as an informal publicity (Figure 11). Leveling also uses its own tectonic potential as a setting for publicity, transforming it into a tribune used in different temporal usages (Figure 12). These situations reveal the effect of the user profile, which is the most important parameter of micro narratives, and show that informality provides an environment for different public activities when the necessary tools and joints are provided.

Figure 11 - Section collage of a leveling part with the orchards.

Figure 12 - Section collage of a leveling part with the tribunes.

The walls that constitute a large part of the Istanbul City Walls are considered as a surface within the scope of the research. Due to its size, it has been observed that different uses have been formed informally and formally, even in a way to serve different organisms. It is also evident in these regions that informality is not entirely public. Each surface and area that is open to human occupation is also suitable for privatization. As the interventions in this context reach a structural dimension, the gaps on the surface turn into extensions of the house for property owners (Figure 13) and temporary shelter areas for urban users (Figure 14).

Figure 13 - Section collage of the intervention of property owners.

Figure 14 - Section collage of an occupation of a surface of the wall.

Cases where the surface is considered as a public space are shaped by both sociability and the basic needs of life. According to the textures such as cafes and sports fields in the neighborhood, micro interventions made by attaching social volumes to the surface transform these spaces into public areas where informal micro narratives are formed (Figure 15). Apart from this, while the surface where the fountain is located offers a life practice occupied by plants, it establishes an alternative publicity due to the structure of water that provides sociability among people (Figure 16).

Figure 15 - Section collage of transformation of surface to a social space.

Figure 16 - Section collage of surface occupied with water and plants.

In the damaged and demolished parts of the city wall, a different approach has emerged compared to other sites. This situation has revealed micro-narratives that can be followed with the necessary security measures and shaped according to the sensitivity of the surrounding texture. The spatiality provided by these destroyed areas near the school buildings has been redefined with barricades and warning signs for the safety of children. In this case, the new public spatiality has been subjected to informal interventions and made safe by taking into account the movements and scale of the children (Figure 17&18).

Figure 17 - Section collage of a destructed part of wall with barricades.

Figure 18 - Section collage of a destructed part of wall near school.

The mapping of the temporal and functional uses of these informal usages offers a framework for understanding how urban borders can evolve into spaces of shared agency and inclusivity through everyday acts of adaptation and reinterpretation. The section collages produced revealed the mechanism of informal public spaces as an inventory of micro interventions and micro narratives.

V. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

This study outlines the border as a dynamic phenomenon that constantly evolves, transforms, and renews itself, and it is examined within the context of informal public space using significant aspects such as participation, intervention, and use. The border, as a threshold between distinct physical, social, or political situations, is constantly negotiating its function, allowing for the emergence of informal action. The border's dynamic character allows it to be maintained through everyday actions, interventions, and temporary occupations, resulting in informal public areas. Borders like the City Walls, especially in historically layered cities like Istanbul, serve as zones of negotiation, where historical significance, present urban demands, and local interventions intersect to create informal spatial scenarios. Subsequently, the city walls have been analyzed on various aspects and first of all, how they fit into the existing urban context has been described.

The section collages designed as a method and their continuity on the map enabled a wide synthesis from micro to macro in the City Walls to be investigated. It has been observed that Istanbul's city walls still serve their original function on a large scale, separating the Historical Peninsula from the rest of the city with their massiveness and historical depth. However, at a micro-scale, their meaning shifts, revealing potentials for informal spaces that emerge as distinct nodes. In this context, the study focuses on micro-narratives, showing that each intervention and usage scenario follows specific dynamics rather than randomness, ultimately gaining a public identity. In this context, although the city wall has a potential for renewal arising from its own tectonics, the phenomena that trigger and mobilize this potential are also evaluated as the parameters that constitute informality at the border. As a result, it is possible to say that the Istanbul City Walls, as an informal public space, has entered into a tectonic regeneration process together with the urban context in which it is located, while at the same time changing and transforming its context at all times. Based on the conceptual sets, interventions, tools and users formed here, it is possible to define a repertoire for the transformation of borders and to question how informal public spaces can be formed in future scenarios. Therefore, with this study, how urban spaces can be shaped by micro-scale narratives, the components of the informal and the dynamism of the public space are revealed and an alternative method and scope for contemporary urban research is introduced.

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AUTHOR INFORMATION

Ayşe Eda Adıgüzel

Department of Architecture

Bahçeşehir University

Ihlamur Yıldız Street, No:8, Beşiktaş, Istanbul /

Türkiye

34353 Istanbul - TÜRKİYE

Tel: +90 212 381 55 32

e-mail: ayseeda.adiguzel@bau.edu.tr

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